

United States Department of the Interior

In Reply Refer to:
08ESMF00-2014-
F-0576-R001

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office
2800 Cottage Way, Suite W-2605
Sacramento, California 95825-1846

Mr. Boris Deunert
Attn: Tom Holstein
Department of Transportation
111 Grand Avenue
P.O. Box 23660
Oakland, California 94623-0660

OCT - 8 2015

Subject: Reinitiation of Formal Consultation on the Proposed Sonoma-Marin Area Rail Transit (SMART) Non-Motorized Multi-use Pathway (NMP) Project Phase 1 in Sonoma and Marin Counties, California (California Department of Transportation (Caltrans) Federal Aid Project Number RPSTPLE 6411 (005))

Dear Mr. Deunert:

This letter is in response to Caltrans's August 25, 2015 request for the reinitiation of formal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) for the SMART NMP Project Phase 1 (proposed project) in Sonoma and Marin Counties, California (Caltrans Federal Aid Project Number RPSTPLE 6411 (005)). At issue are the proposed project's effects on the federally endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*), endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*), threatened California red-legged frog (*Rana draytonii*), and endangered Sonoma Distinct Population Segment (DPS) of the California tiger salamander (Sonoma California tiger salamander) (*Ambystoma californiense*) and its designated critical habitat. Critical habitat has been designated for the California red-legged frog but does not occur within the action area for the proposed project. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

In considering your request, we based our evaluation on the following: (1) the Service's biological opinion on the SMART NMP Project Phase 1 in Sonoma and Marin Counties (Service file number 08ESMF00-2014-F-0576-2), dated March 11, 2015; (2) the August 25, 2015 letter from Caltrans requesting the reinitiation of formal consultation; (3) the June 12, 2015 meeting among the Service, Caltrans, SMART, ICF International, and Area West Environmental; (4) the August 19, 2015 memorandum from ICF International to Caltrans regarding proposed reductions in the amount of Sonoma California tiger salamander habitat compensation (ICF International *in litt.* 2015); and (5) other information available to the Service.

The following additions are made to the **Consultation History** on page 2 of the March 11, 2015 biological opinion:

March 11, 2015 The Service issued the biological opinion for the proposed project (Service file number 08ESMF00-2014-F-0576-2).

- May 12, 2015 The Service received via electronic mail from SMART the request to amend the biological opinion.
- June 12, 2015 The Service attended a meeting among Caltrans, SMART, ICF International, and Area West Environmental to discuss amending the biological opinion for the proposed project.
- August 4, 2015 The Service provided comments on the draft June 12, 2015 meeting notes.
- August 25, 2015 The Service received the letter from Caltrans requesting the reinitiation of formal consultation on the proposed project. The reinitiation request letter also included the August 19, 2015 memorandum from ICF International to Caltrans regarding proposed reductions in the amount of Sonoma California tiger salamander habitat compensation (ICF International *in litt.* 2015).

The Service removes the following General Conservation Measures in the **Conservation Measures** on page 15 of the March 11, 2015 biological opinion:

6. Habitat Restoration Plan: SMART will develop a habitat restoration plan to replace impacted wetlands and waters. A separate habitat restoration plan will be prepared for the pathway (see the *Mitigation and Monitoring Plan for the SMART Project* in Appendix H in the Biological Assessment). Final mitigation ratios will depend on quality of sites impacted and location of mitigation lands (*i.e.*, on or off-site).
7. Wetland Mitigation: To replace impacted wetlands, a habitat restoration plan shall be developed and implemented.
8. Oak Woodland Mitigation: In areas where oaks or other protected trees cannot be avoided, SMART will replace trees removed with the same native tree species at a minimum 3:1 ratio, or as required by applicable ordinance(s). An oak woodland restoration plan shall be developed and provided to CDFW for concurrence. The plan shall include the total acreage of temporary and permanent impacts to all oak woodland habitat. Areas shall be mapped using aerial photographs and provided to CDFW for concurrence. All temporary and permanently disturbed areas shall be mitigated at a 1:1 ratio for creation and preservation of new oak woodlands or a 3:1 ratio for preservation of existing habitat. Sites should be maintained in perpetuity and managed under an approved management plan.

The Service removes Term and Condition Number 2 on page 68 of the March 11, 2015 biological opinion:

Remove:

2. Caltrans shall ensure that SMART has an onsite revegetation and monitoring plan with photo documentation, annual reporting, success criteria, and invasive plant species control reviewed and approved by the Service prior to the initiation of construction of the proposed project. The onsite revegetation and monitoring plan should include the planting of high tide refugia cover (*e.g.*, marsh gumplant) within suitable tidal marsh/transition zone habitat for the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.

The Service changes Term and Condition Number 3 on page 68 of the March 11, 2015 biological opinion:

From:

3. Caltrans shall ensure that SMART has an ongoing invasive plant species control plan, litter cleanup plan, and leash law enforcement plan for the SMART NMP reviewed and approved by the Service prior to the initiation of construction of the proposed project. Caltrans shall ensure that prior to the initiation of construction of the proposed project that SMART has identified sufficient funding to implement these long-term plans.

To:

3. Caltrans shall ensure that SMART has an ongoing invasive plant species control plan, litter cleanup plan, and leash law enforcement plan for the SMART NMP reviewed and approved by the Service. These plans, which may be included with a single NMP Maintenance of Way Plan, shall be submitted to the Service prior to beginning construction of the first NMP segment and will be reviewed and approved by the Service within six months of beginning construction of the first NMP segment. Caltrans shall ensure that prior to the initiation of construction of the proposed project that SMART has identified sufficient funding to implement these long-term plans.

The Service changes Term and Condition Number 4 on page 68 of the March 11, 2015 biological opinion:

From:

4. Caltrans shall ensure that the long-term management plans at the Mira Monte property and the Phelan Conservation Area are reviewed and approved by the Service prior to the initiation of construction of the proposed project. The long-term management plans shall include long-term plans for monitoring California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse populations, controlling invasive plant species, restoring high-tide refugia/transition zone habitat (*e.g.*, planting marsh gumplant), controlling mammalian predators, and removing raptor perches for the benefit of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail. The conservation easements shall be recorded with a fully funded endowment under a Service-approved plan within 12 months of the start of construction of the proposed project and prior to the introduction of NMP traffic.

To:

4. Caltrans shall ensure that the long-term management plans at the Mira Monte property and the Phelan Conservation Area are reviewed and approved by the Service prior to the initiation of construction of the proposed project. The long-term management plans shall include long-term plans for monitoring California clapper rail presence/absence, controlling invasive plant species, restoring high-tide refugia/transition zone habitat (*e.g.*, planting marsh gumplant), controlling mammalian predators, and removing raptor perches for the benefit of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail. The conservation easements shall be recorded with a fully funded endowment under a Service-approved plan within 12 months of the start of construction of the proposed project and prior to the introduction of NMP traffic.

The reinitiation request letter from Caltrans dated August 25, 2015 also stated that SMART would like to revisit the Sonoma California tiger salamander habitat loss and compensation calculations submitted in the Biological Assessment for the proposed project and carried through in the biological opinion. The request refers to a memorandum from ICF International dated August 19, 2015 (ICF International *in litt.* 2015). The memorandum states that SMART believes that the Sonoma California tiger salamander habitat loss that was identified in the Biological Assessment north of mile post (MP) 50.1 (0.15 mile south of Todd Road in the City of Santa Rosa, Sonoma County), totaling approximately 4.75 acres, should not be included in the effects reported in the biological opinion. The memorandum states that while designated critical habitat for the Sonoma California tiger salamander extends north to MP 53.3, suitable Sonoma California tiger salamander habitat terminates at MP 50.1 (ICF International *in litt.* 2015). According to SMART the proposed project footprint remains within critical habitat until MP 53.3 but is essentially surrounded by development after MP 50.1 and would not provide suitable habitat (ICF International *in litt.* 2015). For the reasons set out in the memorandum, SMART proposes that the biological opinion be changed to state that the total amount of Sonoma California tiger salamander habitat that will be permanently lost be reduced from 7.56 acres to 2.81 acres. The Sonoma California tiger salamander compensation ratio would remain 2:1. Therefore, SMART proposes that the total amount of Sonoma California tiger salamander habitat compensation be reduced from 15.12 acres to 5.62 acres. The compensation would be purchased from one of the approved mitigation banks within the Santa Rosa Plain Conservation Strategy Planning Area.

The Service does not agree with SMART's conclusion that the proposed project footprint for the NMP north of MP 50.1 does not provide suitable habitat for the Sonoma California tiger salamander. There are many known occurrences of the Sonoma California tiger salamander within between 0.1 mile and 0.5 mile of the NMP right-of-way north of MP 50.1 between Todd Road and Hearn Avenue (California Natural Diversity Database occurrence numbers 483, 725, 780, 786, 788, 790, 926, 1105, and 1134; California Department of Fish and Wildlife 2015). Orloff (2007) found that the majority of California tiger salamanders dispersed at least 0.5 mile from the breeding site, with a smaller number of salamanders appearing to move even farther—from 0.75 to 1.3 miles between breeding ponds and upland habitat. Therefore, the NMP right-of-way north of MP 50.1 is within dispersal distance of many known occurrences of the Sonoma California tiger salamander. The developed areas and roads surrounding portions of the NMP in this area do not create a barrier to Sonoma California tiger salamander dispersal across the NMP right-of-way. There are a number of areas immediately adjacent to the NMP right-of-way north of MP 50.1 that provide suitable upland refugia and dispersal habitat for the Sonoma California tiger salamander where small, open undeveloped parcels are present and generally contiguous with the NMP right-of-way. Therefore, the Service will not change the estimate of the amount of Sonoma California tiger salamander habitat that will be permanently lost by the proposed project. The total amount of Sonoma California tiger salamander habitat compensation will remain 15.12 acres.

Conclusion

The above changes to the biological opinion for the proposed SMART NMP Project Phase 1 do not change the Service's conclusion that the proposed SMART NMP Project Phase 1, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the salt marsh harvest mouse, California clapper rail, California red-legged frog, and Sonoma California tiger salamander.

The above changes to the biological opinion for the proposed SMART NMP Project Phase 1 do not change the Service's conclusion that the proposed SMART NMP Project Phase 1, as proposed, is not likely to destroy or adversely modify designated critical habitat for the Sonoma California tiger

salamander.

This concludes formal consultation on the SMART NMP Project Phase 1 in Sonoma and Marin Counties, California. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16, reinitiation of formal consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service where discretionary Federal agency involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and: (a) if the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded; (b) if new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered; (c) if the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion; or (d) if a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

If you have questions concerning this reinitiation of the biological opinion for the SMART NMP Project Phase 1 in Sonoma and Marin Counties, California, please contact Joseph Terry, Senior Biologist, or Ryan Olah, Coast/Bay Division Chief, at the letterhead address, at telephone number (916) 414-6623, or email joseph_terry@fws.gov or ryan_olah@fws.gov.

Sincerely,

Jennifer M. Norris
Field Supervisor

cc:

Karen Weiss, California Department of Fish and Wildlife, Napa, California
Xavier Fernandez, San Francisco Bay Regional Water Quality Control Board, Oakland, California
Bill Gamlen, Sonoma-Marin Area Rail Transit District, Petaluma, California
Dan Logan, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration/National Marine Fisheries Service,
Santa Rosa, California
Bryan Matsumoto, U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, San Francisco, California
Michelle Tovar, Area West Environmental, Inc., Orangevale, California

LITERATURE CITED

California Department of Fish and Wildlife. 2015. California Natural Diversity Database. RareFind version 5. Natural Heritage Division. Sacramento, California.

Orloff, S.G. 2007. Migratory movements of California tiger salamander in upland habitat – A five-year study, Pittsburg, California. Prepared for Bailey Estates LLC. 47 + pp.

In Litt.

ICF International. 2015. Letter from Leslie Allen, Project Manager, ICF International, San Francisco, California, to Tom Holstein, California Department of Transportation, District 4 Office of Local Assistance, Oakland, California, dated August 19, 2015. Subject: SMART Non-Motorized Pathway—Proposed reduction in California tiger salamander impacts and mitigation documented in current biological opinion.